

THE NECESSITY OF REGIONAL COOPERATION IN CENTRAL ASIA AND ITS STAGES OF DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract. Regional cooperation in Central Asia is a key mechanism for Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, and Uzbekistan to address common challenges, promote sustainable development, and strengthen regional stability. The article analyzes the main factors and stages of the development of regional cooperation processes among the countries of Central Asia. With the beginning of regional integration, especially after the collapse of the former Soviet Union in 1991, new principles and initiatives of regional cooperation began to take shape. The article also discusses the main areas aimed at further deepening political, economic and cultural ties between the countries of Central Asia, in particular, security, equitable distribution of water resources and transboundary projects.

Key words: Cooperation, Central Asia, Uzbekistan, region, global power, institutions, integration.

Central Asia is one of the oldest cradles of human civilization, famous for its rich history of statehood spanning more than 3,000 years. In different historical periods, this region has been given different names. The term “Central Asia” only became popular in the 1980s. [1]

Western scholars use the term Central Asia in a broad sense, including Mongolia, southern Siberia, Kazakhstan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan, northern Afghanistan, the Herat region of Iran, Tibet, Xinjiang, and Gansu. However, at a meeting in Tashkent on January 4, 1993, the leaders of Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Kazakhstan, and Kyrgyzstan officially recognized the geographical boundaries of Central Asia and officially recognized

these five republics as part of it. Today, Central Asia covers an area of 4 million square kilometers and is home more than 82,8 million people. The region is of great importance in the international arena due to its vast natural resources, economic potential, social characteristics and rich cultural heritage. It has made a significant contribution to the development of humanity and continues to play its role today. Joint efforts are the most effective way for the countries of the region to achieve development, take a worthy place in the international community and solve problems. There are also different approaches to the concept of regional cooperation. Some researchers understand it as the disappearance of borders, while others see it as a process of integration into a single political and economic structure. Still others define regional cooperation as a process of strengthening political and economic ties between participating states. In any case, the concept of regional cooperation does not have a single definition, but most recognize it as a means of creating new opportunities for participants. Therefore, regional cooperation is considered a process arising from objective necessity, based on the principles of equality and harmony of common interests. This process includes complex actions aimed at strengthening cooperation between countries and regional integration.

First of all, it is necessary to recognize that regional cooperation has different models and forms. This, on the one hand, is due to the goals and objectives of cooperation, and on the other hand, it is related to the capabilities of the participants in the process, national interests and the diversity of the region. Also, the variability of the demands of the time and regional factors affect this process.

When analyzing the processes of cooperation in Central Asia and the stages of its development, the views of F. Tolipov are noteworthy. According to him, the processes of regional cooperation in the region began in 1990 and went through several important stages:

1. The first stage (July 1990 - May 1993)

Before the collapse of the USSR, in July 1990, the leaders of five Central Asian states met in Almaty to discuss existing problems. At this stage, the initial forms of cooperation were formed.

2. The second stage (July 1993 - December 1995)

During this period, the economic and political system of the region was significantly strengthened. Close cooperative relations between the Central Asian states developed.

3. The third stage (December 15, 1995 - September 11, 2001)

This stage brought the cooperation processes in the region to a new level, during which the focus on security and stability increased.

4. The fourth stage (2001 - 2005)

After the global events of 2001, the countries of the region sought to further strengthen their ties. This stage is significant in that it was aimed at revising the mechanisms of cooperation and making them more effective [4].

In general, the roots of cooperation in Central Asia go back a long way. The peoples of the region have long been united by a common culture, civilization and the need to jointly fight against external forces. Central Asia's geographical location, at the crossroads of East and West, has always made it an attractive area for external invaders. Looking at the history of the region, we can see that over the past 2,000 years, at various times, it has been ruled by Alexander the Great, the Arabs, the Mongols, and Russia. During the struggle against these invaders, the peoples of the region have overcome their oppression by coming together and cooperating. Therefore, the roots of regional integration, unlike in Europe, are rooted in a long history. While the peoples of the region have sought to unite in their own interests, external invaders have sought to undermine their unity based on the principle of "divide and rule." The division of Central Asia into five republics during the Soviet era, as well as into five regions during the Russian dictatorship, are clear evidence of this policy. After the countries of the region gained independence, cooperation processes began to take shape on the basis of

new principles and procedures. In this case, the state and authorities acted as the initiators of the process.

Cooperation processes in the region can be conditionally divided into three periods:

1. The first period (from 1991 to the beginning of the new century):

This period covers the formation of cooperation processes on the basis of new procedures. States acted as the main subjects in this process. In June 1990, the leaders of the five republics met in Almaty and agreed to cooperate in the political, economic and social spheres. Although an agreement was signed in Tashkent on August 14, 1991 on the establishment of an inter-republican advisory council, this initiative was not implemented as a result of the collapse of the USSR. Also, at the meeting of the heads of governments of Central Asia and Kazakhstan in April 1992, it was agreed to establish an inter-state investment fund and an investment bank. However, the experience of subsequent years has shown that implementing integration in one area is not enough. At a meeting in Tashkent in January 1993, an agreement was signed on the establishment of a common market, and the term "Central Asia" was widely used in scientific circles.

2. The second period (from the new century to 2017):

This period is characterized by the variability of the dynamics of cooperation processes in the region. Cooperation between states sometimes intensified, sometimes decreased. Global geopolitical processes, regional economic and political interests, and external pressures played an important role in this.

3. The third period (from 2017 to the present):

This period reflects new trends in regional cooperation. Mutual relations are further strengthened, and a number of initiatives have been implemented that give impetus to integration processes. Great importance was attached to joint action between the countries of the region in the political, economic, and cultural spheres [5].

In September 2017, at the 72nd session of the UN General Assembly, the Republic of Uzbekistan put forward new initiatives to ensure security and stability among the Central Asian states. These initiatives are aimed at deepening cooperation between the countries of the region and jointly solving regional problems. For all-round successful cooperation, Uzbekistan also proposed holding regular consultative meetings of the heads of Central Asian states. As a result of this initiative, the first consultative meeting of the heads of Central Asian states was held in Astana in March 2018. The establishment of a consultation platform, in turn, was an important step in ensuring security and stability in the region, as this cooperation can create an opportunity to establish regular consultations and cooperation between the heads of state.

In November 2017, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev spoke about the important tasks of strengthening regional cooperation at the International Conference on Central Asia organized under the auspices of the UN in Samarkand. He also identified 6 areas for strengthening ties between the Central Asian countries and resolving issues related to trade and economy, transport, transit and logistics, ensuring security and stability, and state borders. Among these areas, issues related to ensuring peace and security are of particular importance. Ensuring peace, tranquility and economic development in Central Asia are set as the highest goal and task for Uzbekistan.

At the same time, the President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev put forward a proposal to organize a Regional Economic Forum and an Association of Leaders and Business Communities of Central Asian Countries in order to further deepen trade and economic ties between the Central Asian countries and create favorable conditions for increasing trade turnover. As a result of this proposal, the Council of Border Regions between the Central Asian countries was established and is successfully operating [3]. These initiatives and practices are one of the important steps towards stability, cooperation and socio-economic development in Central Asia.

In recent years, relations between the countries of Central Asia have developed differently. [3] While some countries have tried to get closer and strengthen cooperation, others have been passive in this process and have not been able to achieve sufficient results in jointly solving problems. The reasons for this are related to various factors.

The first factor is that the peoples of the region have lived in dependence on others for more than 130 years, living under their thumb, and their thirst for freedom, independence, and the fact that they are now beginning to breathe freely and their desire to demonstrate their "I" have become more prominent in the general interests of the region.

The second reason is that the political leaders of some countries, despite historical and geographical realities, claim the antiquity of their peoples and strive for leadership. They try to justify this by relying on their own time in the formation of other peoples in the region, which leads to mutual contradictions.

The third factor is related to the strategic importance of Central Asia in the international arena and its rich resources. This region is a place where the interests of leading states clash, and even after gaining independence, the countries in the region have intensified their competition for their wealth.

The fourth factor is the continuation of political, social and economic instability in some countries. This, in turn, has had a negative impact on regional cooperation and stability. Also, as can be seen from these factors, cooperation between states is not only an objective necessity, but also a process that meets regional development and national interests. Today's global crisis, socio-political instability, as well as national and spiritual impoverishment further increase the importance of cooperation in the region.

In conclusion, cooperation between the countries of Central Asia and its development depend on many political, economic and cultural factors. Central Asia is of great importance in global and regional politics due to its natural resources and strategic location, which leads to a clash of interests of these forces. The

relations between the countries that have gained independence are sometimes complicated by attempts to strengthen their positions in international politics. At the same time, the development of regional cooperation between the countries of Central Asia depends on the implementation of positive initiatives aimed at ensuring their internal stability, deepening economic ties and strengthening security. The common interests of the region, in particular, peace, stability and economic development, are the main directions, which serve to develop mutual trust and cooperation between the countries. In this regard, the success of regional cooperation between the countries of Central Asia requires the readiness of each country to combine its political will and socio-economic capabilities. This, in turn, will be of great importance in ensuring peace in the region and creating a prosperous future.

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